

CURRENT PROBLEMS OF DRUG ADDICTION PREVENTION AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract. *The article highlights the current problems of drug addiction prevention among young people, factors contributing to the emergence and emergence of drug addiction or drug addiction, as well as measures taken to prevent the use of these substances among young people.*

Keywords: *Drugs, psychotropic substances, legal awareness, law, crime, prevention.*

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ НАРКОМАНИИ СРЕДИ МОЛОДЕЖИ

Анотация. *В статье освещаются актуальные проблемы профилактики наркомании среди молодежи, факторы, способствующие возникновению и зарождению наркозависимости или пристрастия к наркотикам, а также меры, принимаемые для предотвращения употребления этих веществ среди молодежи.*

Ключевые слова: *Наркотики, психотропные вещества, правосознание, закон, преступность, профилактика.*

Although strict measures are being taken against drug trafficking and consumption in our country, today illegal circulation of drugs among young people remains one of the most dangerous and pressing problems. Drug dealers continue to use new methods and tricks to sell the killer poison. They are taking the lives of young people who have not yet formed a worldview and are prone to being influenced by others in order to achieve their nefarious goals.

In this regard, the President of the country Sh.M. Mirziyoev said, "In today's difficult times, raising young people to become physically and spiritually perfect people remains an extremely important task for us!" - he emphasized [1].

Young people should have a strong and strong faith, but also a healthy body and mind, able to withstand any difficulties and hardships. The threat of drug addiction to the health of young people, to families, to morals, to all spheres of human life is increasing day by day and hour by hour. When talking about the factors that lead to the beginning and origin of drug addiction, it is necessary to pay attention to the following: First: addiction to drugs, youth situations are important. For example, depression, nervousness, lack of self-control, lack of will, inability to meet one's own needs, inability to cope with some life difficulties. Secondly: the future physical and spiritual formation of the young generation mainly depends on the environment in the family, who the parents are, what place they occupy in the family, the mutual treatment of the couple, and the educational work they carry out in the comprehensive formation of their child. Thirdly: life shows that in the maturation of the young generation, in entering a certain useful good or bad path, the surrounding friends and relatives, especially the friends in that environment, have a great influence. Therefore, it is very important to monitor where and with whom they are, what they are doing, what friends they have in the family, in the upbringing of young people. The fight against

drug addiction, which can endanger human life and the future of the young generation, is considered one of the important tasks of every citizen of our independent country, moreover, of each of us. After all, it is our task, our honorable duty to eliminate and prevent any harmful evil in the life of society. Criminological scientists say that the environment in the family plays an important role in the formation of personality. In particular, according to Yu.M.Antonyan, one of the main reasons for crimes committed by young people in the family is the parents' lack of love for their children, their neglect of their upbringing. Depriving young people of kindness in childhood creates feelings of anxiety, fear, and hatred in their psyche. These feelings are unconsciously registered and lead to maladaptive behavior, including, in its most extreme form, youth crime in the family[2].

Unfortunately, nowadays there are cases of consumption of drugs containing narcotics (—Tramadol, —Nalbuphine, etc.) and psychoactive drugs (—Lyrica, —Regapen, —Galara, etc.) It is a pity that despite the fact that all conditions have been created for them to become physically healthy, to acquire modern knowledge and profession, they commit drug-related crimes and enter the path of drug addiction.[3].

Today, the fight against drug addiction and its prevention has risen to the level of state policy in Uzbekistan. It is especially noteworthy that the activities and initiatives carried out by the President are being promoted in this regard. Within the framework of the "Month against drug addiction among young people", various events, round talks and meetings are being held in all cities and districts of our Republic on prevention of drug addiction among young people, fight against this type of crime, early prevention of drug-related offenses. In particular, in schools and lyceums in many cities and districts of our Republic, video clips, slides and banners depicting the negative effects of drug addiction and the serious consequences it can cause are displayed. Due to the fact that our young people are unknowingly falling into the vortex of this evil, and as a result of this, many disappointments and crimes are taking place, propaganda work is being carried out among the youth.[4].

It is conveyed to young people that drug addiction is a tool that leads to untimely death, and every young person should be careful not to fall into the trap of this pitiful disease. should not be indifferent to those around them, because it is a threat to the people who consume the grain, to those who are engaged in its trade, but also to the whole society. That's why every year June 26 is declared as "International Day against Drug Abuse". In this regard, events are constantly being held in our Republic. In particular, in universities, lyceums and colleges, schools and other educational institutions, events are held in cooperation with representatives of all fields, and explanatory work is regularly conducted among young people. The most valuable wealth for a person is health. Its preservation is entrusted to each of us. In the religion of Islam, the preservation and protection of human life, mind and health is considered one of the most important goals. In addition to endangering human development and faith, drug use has a very negative impact on the development and progress of our independent country.

When talking about the factors that cause the beginning and origin of drug addiction or addiction, the following should be taken into account:

First: addiction to drugs, the circumstances of the person are important in becoming addicted to it. For example, depression, nervousness, lack of self-control, lack of will, inability to satisfy one's own demand, inability to cope with some life difficulties.

Secondly: the future physical and spiritual formation of the young generation mainly depends on the environment in the family, who the parents are, what place they occupy in the family, the mutual treatment of the spouses, and the educational work they carry out in the comprehensive formation of their child. Thirdly: life shows that in the maturation of the young generation, in entering a certain useful good or bad path, the influence of the surrounding comrades, relatives, especially the comrades in that environment, is great.

That is why it is very important to control where and with whom they are together, what they are doing, what kind of friends they have.

At a time when great changes are taking place in our country, young people are becoming more and more active in the life of the society and are gaining their place, it worries all of us that some of our weak-willed teenagers are suffering from drug addiction. After all, as much as it destroys the human body, it also does unprecedented damage to society. This disease, which is called the plague of the century, destroys peaceful families, makes children orphans, and forces them to live in need and poverty. And the result will certainly end tragically.

We all know that a person who begins to use drugs, of any kind, first develops a habit. But after a year, the addict becomes unfit for work. As a result, he is forced to resort to crime. That is, in order to receive the next drug, he starts stealing from his home - his family [5].

In addition, drug addiction also causes the spread of serious and incurable diseases such as AIDS, hepatitis, and tuberculosis.

The whole world community is worried about the fact that drug addiction and drug trafficking are causing great damage to the education of the young generation and the future of humanity. Therefore, the fight against this disaster has now become one of the global problems on Earth.

The fight against drug addiction, which can jeopardize human life and the future of the young generation, is one of the important tasks of every citizen of our independent country. After all, it is our task, our honorable duty to eliminate and prevent any harmful evil in the life of society.

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